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On Religions

&

Albanians across the Semitic faiths

(An essay by Agron Elezi – Gjilan, July 2019)

To my child

Introduction

The essay on religions arises from my philosophical reflection, beginning with their origins, as humanity's continuous striving in search of meaning and absolute truth. It traces the evolution of religion from mythology and early philosophy toward monotheistic revelation. In this context, religion is analyzed and defined as a necessary response to the limitations of human consciousness when confronted with fundamental questions and with the paradox of the infinite unknown.

The essay then proceeds to describe the early spread of Christianity in Illyricum, the impact of Slavic incursions, and the Albanian tragedy during the Great Schism, highlighting the principal cause: the absence and delay of an autocephalous Orthodox Church in the Albanian language. The existential consequences were devastating, including the erosion of Albanian identity and historical memory, whereby antiquity and the names of heroes were extensively absorbed into religious frameworks by neighboring peoples.

Positioned in the "paradise of Europe," at the crossroads between East and West, and despite conversions to Orthodoxy, Catholicism, and Islam, Albanians preserved their continuity through the Kanun, an ethical code standing above religious affiliation. The essay also illuminates Albanian contributions to both Christian and Islamic civilizations through an integrative and humanistic approach to religion.

Finally, through historical evidence, the essay argues that religion, when instrumentalized as a political dogma, becomes destructive. Yet as a moral and existential framework, it remains a source of inner repose and spiritual stability. From the analysis of this evidence, Albanians emerge as a model of cultural resilience, religious tolerance, and ethical cohesion rooted in antiquity. They endured centuries of conflict and resisted prolonged periods of political dogmatism, at the very epicenter of clashes between expansionist religious denominations. This came at a tremendous cost: from a population once extending across the entire Balkan Peninsula and into parts of Asia, only two small centers remain today - Albania and Kosovo.

Their sacrifice and survival constitute an example of unimaginable resilience, physical as well as spiritual and moral, rich with heroes who transcend every dimension of the traditional heroic archetype. Perhaps only a people belonging to the pantheon of Pyrrhus, Alexander the Great, and Skanderbeg could withstand such an invading storm from all directions of the world. Or perhaps this is because from the same pantheon emerged Mother Teresa (Anjezë Gonxhe Bojaxhiu), the "great-granddaughter of the oracles of Dodona," a profound heir to the ancient divine-religious tradition, and the highest expression of spiritual and moral heroism. Thus, throughout their extraordinary history, Albanians embody both of these great forms of heroism. They have demonstrated that true heroism and the survival of a people are measured not only by the battles they win, but also by the values they bestow.

This essay on religions, through historical, philosophical, and ethical approaches, offers unique, impartial, and valuable insights that remain relevant to the modern era.

Author – Agron Elezi

Prologue: An Archaic Invocation

O ye muses! Goddesses of my blood! Grant me the strength and wisdom to clearly express the reason and essence of our arduous, compelling, and centuries-old striving to find the true path of fulfillment.

Ye, my ancestors! Builders of the temples of the deities! Bless me! Fill me with courage and honor, that I may present the depth and height of faith.

And You - My wife, My love! Light for me the glow of your candle, so that I may remain illuminated and pure, and not sink into the devilish mud along the journey.

Resolution for our immortal and indefinite soul in our mortal and definite guise

The human soul, our consciousness & subconscious, through the unstoppable gallop of time, from the caves to the skyscrapers, from stone tools to the quantum processors of our days, has constantly and insatiably searched for the truth, for an absolute explanation of its existence and the sensations that surround it. Who we are? Why are we here? How was the world created? Is there life after death...?

All these fundamental questions have been raised by the soul over the centuries, trying to find answers while sailing rivers, seas, and oceans, encountering new horizons again

and again, as a wondrous, never-ending adventure and experience, passing from one civilization to another, from one culture to the next.

The mythological visions of the world flourished over many centuries - to aid the soul - since the discovery of fire, perhaps even earlier. Faith, despite reason, proved to be a central factor in providing the spiritual support so necessary for the human being, as a creature distinct from the animal world. When science was still in its infancy, mythology was the spiritual and mental compass of humanity. Thus, in that delicate threshold of development, where man had just begun to rise above instinct and strive to understand the laws of the world, mythology became the first form - and an inexhaustible source - not only for the religions that would follow, but also for philosophy, science, and art all at once. Through it, the existential questions mentioned earlier - and others such as: "why do misfortunes happen?" and "how should we act?" - took shape and found answers.

The temple of Dodona in Epirus, as one of the oldest oracles in Europe where "the divine language was spoken" - as described by ancient authors - was not merely a place of religious worship. It was a center of knowledge of its time, a place where people sought to understand the direction they should take in life, before a war, a marriage, or a state decision. And these, the first priests did not accomplish through written word or logical argument, but through the language of symbols.

In this way, mythology and the oracle were not simply “superstitions”; they represented a sublime effort to impose order upon chaos, to make the terrifying world predictable and comprehensible, and at the same time to ease humanity's struggle for existence. They functioned as a system of interpretation that, though mystical and drawn from the depths of the subconscious, aimed to fill the void where today we place formulas, theories, and scientific analysis.

When a new civilization emerged, the soul turned its gaze toward the first philosophers. They aimed to find natural explanations through reason (consciousness), rather than supernatural ones through the subconscious, for nature and the phenomena surrounding them. As a fundamental answer to existence, philosophers claimed the source of everything must be fire or water - or, as Democritus proposed, that everything is made of tiny, invisible, eternal, and indivisible particles called atoms. But then arose the question: Who created fire? Water? The atom?

Even in our times, where we can reason and define the expanding universe, black holes, dark matter, quantum field theory, and quarks—the smallest units we have discovered in our scientific quest—a multitude of new and much more complex questions arise. We still fail to uncover the grand formula of the universe, the truth.

From the beginning, the soul has faced the paradox of endless questions - endless reasoning and explanations, desperately trying to grasp the unknown and define it as

the known. The more we know, the more we are confronted by the unknown. And at the edge of this reasoning, Socrates declared: "I am the wisest man alive, for I know one thing - that I know nothing."

Understanding that the unknown cannot be grasped by means of the known, we arrive at the Semites—who ingeniously solved the problem of the unknown. Through the visions (subconscious) of Abraham, Jesus, and Muhammad, they realized that the endless unknown can only be solved by the unknown.

The three Semitic religions - Judaism, Christianity, and Islam - share the same solution (the universal idea of truth): that there is only One God, the "Universal Unknown," the Eternal Spirit, the Infinite Mind, who can play with space and time, who created the world, and who will one day bring it to an end (the Day of Judgment). The thirst for the problem of existence, the thirst for the infinite unknown, and the anxiety over life and death can only be quenched by the "Universal Unknown," and this is the Almighty God. Only with Him can our infinite and ever-searching soul find peace.

The Holy Scriptures, such as the Old Testament and the Qur'an, were written in languages of the same Semitic family. In the Old Testament, we can find a word for God with the same semantic root as that in Islam. These three major brotherly religions share a common origin—the city of Jerusalem as their sacred center.

In contrast to the Semites, stand the two great religions of the Far East: Hinduism and Buddhism. They believe that God, the Infinite Mind, resides within man (in contrast to the Semitic view, in which God is outside man and singular). Man can become one with God through spiritual enlightenment, by practicing deep self-reflection or meditation, and thus will find the truth, or peace.

Some of the great figures and the approaches of Albanians toward Semitic culture

Throughout history, Albanians, with their location between East and West, in the middle of frequent clashes of civilizations, were constantly faced with disasters of wars, barbarian or imperial invasions; challenging new cultures; cults, mits, religions, etc. Keeping their code (kanun) as a primary measure of their ethics, they accepted the main religions of the world - Christianity, and Islam. Through the words of the messengers of God, it was welcomed and appreciated the stories on our genesis, roles, fulfillment, and after-world destinations. Furthermore, the idea was very inspirational and sparked off the whole new creative spirit of our early artists, whether musicians, painters, or poets. It was Pjetër Bogdani (Petro Bogdano: 1630-1689) an Albanian writer born in Prizren of Kosova, with his masterpiece “Çeta e Profetëve” (Cuneus Prophetarum) written in both Latin and Epirotic (Albanian) language,

who has introduced deeply the religious vision to Albanian people – the “knowledge of God, an unraveling of the problem of existence.” Furthermore, since the book is also covering philosophy and science, “it is a humanist work of the Baroque age steeped in the philosophical traditions of Plato, Aristotle, St Augustine, and St Thomas Aquinas” - as Robert Elsie (1950-2017) quoted.

They have given four popes to the Vatican: Pope St Eleutherius (175-189), St Caius (283-296), John IV (640-642), Clement XI (1700-1721), and the world heroine of compassion - Mother Teresa (Anjezë Gonxhe Bojaxhiu (1910-1997), born in Shkup, now the capital of North Macedonia, then part of the Kosovo Vilayet of the Ottoman Empire.

On the other hand, they became prominent imams to Islam and were the founders of modern Muslim states like Egypt and Turkey. It is quite reasonable and acceptable that people with rich cultural backgrounds, and due to the influence of their code, would have a kind of gentle approach to Semitic religions. And so, they were the first to contribute to the formation of modern Islamic states, as opposed to fundamentalist ones.

At the beginning of the XIX AD, an Albanian Ottoman military officer, Mohammed Ali, seized control over the holy city of Jerusalem for his account, and established his son, Ibrahim Pasha, as ruler of Syria and Palestine. As per historian Simon Sebag Montefiore – the Albanian conquest of the holy city eased the repression of Jewish, promising

equality under the law, and several synagogues were built for the first time with official permission. Albanian people were classified as a noble race by the Third Reich. At the same time, this race, during the Second World War - thanks to privileges and due to their gracious hospitality and compassion engraved in their code - hid some of the Jewish families in their homes, saving them from the holocaust.

The Spread of Christianity in Illyricum and the Slavic invasions

*(And know that I am with you always; yes, to the end of time-
Matthew 28:20)*

About the year 57, Saint Paul wrote: "Thus from Jerusalem to Illyria I performed the ministry of the resurrection of Christ, trying to evangelize where the name of Christ was not known." Many other saints have preached in the Illyrian territories apart from Paul, passing the Balkans through the Egnatia road to Durrës (Dyrrachium). In Illyria, which included Dardania (present-day Kosovo and beyond), the earliest Christian bishops began their activity, starting with Bishop Caesar of Durrës in 70 and later, St. Astin in 98, who was sentenced to death in 116, by the emperor Trajan and the local ruler, Agricola, as at this time Christianity was illegal and condemned by Rome. From the 1st to the 4th century AD, the first Christian centers were established by the preaching activity of the Illyrian apostles and their supporters.

The complete return of Christianity to Albanian lands took place during the V-VI AD. Saint Jerome (Hieronymus) of Illyria made the first translations of the Bible passages into Latin (La Vulgata) giving the world for the first time the holy book in the early V AD. He translated the Hebrew Bible from the original Hebrew, having previously translated portions from the Septuagint which came from Alexandria. He believed the Septuagint is mistranslated along with its Hellenistic heretical elements. Most Christians, including Augustine, had prioritized the Septuagint translation into Latin – as per them, the Septuagint sounds more inspiring.

Bishop Nicetas of Remesiana, located in the northern part of Dardania, is the creator of the prayer of Christianity “Te Deum laudamus” that continues to be one of the major prayers even today after sixteen centuries.

The arrival of the Slavs in the VI century AD in the Balkans increased the ethnic diversity in the Balkans and today is a formative element that laid the foundations of Balkanization. "Slavs have no heroic legend to recall their settlement on the Balkan Peninsula," writes Czech Professor Dvornik.

Historian W. Temperly writes: “The Slavs did not come as an invading army that could be fought with weapons but as a mass of people against whom there was no power that could stand. It was easy to exterminate individuals or whole groups from Slavic invaders, but it was impossible

to stop their invasions, where the number was so large that it took the place of warlike features."

While the Arbëresh historian from Croatia, Aleksandër Stipčević, about the Slavic invasions and settlements in Illyricum wrote: "The end of the old times and the beginning of the Middle Ages continued in the Balkans as one of the darkest periods. The Goths, Huns, Avars, and other barbarian peoples attacked from all parts, plundering and destroying everything created by the Romans and Illyrians during those centuries of labor and progress. A developed civilization began to disappear under the deadly blows inflicted by the barbarian hordes with their destructive rage. At the beginning of the 7th century, colonization began by various Slavic peoples, who, little by little, occupied almost the entire land that once belonged to the Illyrians."

Unlike other barbaric invasions that did not take place in Illyria, the arrival of the Slavs had great consequences for the Illyrian / Albanian people. In the VIII century, Slavic invasions ended in the Balkans. Illyrian settlements narrowed considerably, and the Albanian population living, especially along the Adriatic coast, in places, now called: Slovenia, Croatia, Bosnia, part of Montenegro, Serbia and Macedonia was almost completely assimilated.

The consequences of the great schism

(Miserere Mei, Deus! - Psalm 51)

When the Roman Empire was divided into two zones, Latin-speaking Rome began to claim superiority over Greek-speaking Constantinople. Although the year of the partition is symbolically marked as 1057, according to archival documents, there was a contest between Rome and Constantinople over who would influence the dioceses of Illyria, and these disputes began as early as the eighth century AD and continued for more than six centuries reaching even bloody battles.

The Slavic population at the beginning of their settlement in the Balkans was of the pagan religion. But very soon, they too embraced Christianity, not only as a religion but also as a culture and civilization. Serbs and Bulgarians, along with the great schism, remained with the Orthodox Christian Church, while Croats and Slovenes joined the Catholic Christian Church. Thus the former Illyria was halved into two religious jurisdictions, where Byzantium dominated more. With this division, the Albanian inhabitants of different dialects that were spread throughout the territory of Illyria were also halved. Although a people with a common code and language, as seen later, with this division of Christianity into Orthodox and Catholic, they came out as losers...

With regard to codes of conduct, many of the peoples described as "barbarians" in the Middle Ages - such as the Slavs who settled in the Balkans, the Russians, and the early Germans - lacked elaborated codes of honor prior to

their adoption of a major religion. Their moral frameworks were imported from faith: the Slavs and Russians through Orthodox Christianity, the Germans through Catholic Christianity, and the Turko-Mongol peoples through Islam. Religion thus became the primary source of their moral and juridical norms.

The French and English, and to some extent certain Germanic groups, did possess rudimentary codes of honor prior to the acceptance of Christianity, but these were restricted to the domains of knighthood, aristocracy, or a warrior elite. By contrast, the Albanians required no religious framework to define the principles of honor, *besa* (the pledged word of trust), hospitality, or blood (kinship and vengeance). These values were deeply embedded within their ancient customary code, long before the appearance of either biblical or Qur'anic writings.

This code endured even after the arrival of religion: Albanians preserved the *Kanun* despite converting to Orthodoxy, Catholicism, or Islam, maintaining it until the emergence of the modern state. Furthermore, whereas among the aforementioned peoples the code of honor generally applied only to the social or military elite, among Albanians it extended universally, from peasant to chieftain alike. It is thus unsurprising that the renowned Ottoman historian Ibn Kemal remarked of the Albanians "that even the weakest among them is one of the strongest and bravest," since he, like all others, had been raised under the code.

Since the notion of the nation did not exist at the time, the religious definition of ethnicity with a common language, territory, and folklore was the key to the later definition of national identities. It is worth mentioning the thirsty and rapid conversion of Slavs as pagans to the Semitic religion, and even more so, the early translation of the bible from Greek into Old Church Slavonic which started in 863 by monk Cyril and Methodius - devising the Glagolitic alphabet, the first alphabet used to transcribe Old Church Slavonic. For their work evangelizing the Slavs, they are known as the "Apostles to the Slavs". After Bulgarian, the Serbian Orthodox Church gained autonomy in the early 13th century AD. Monk Sava himself succeeded in persuading Patriarch Manuel I of Constantinople to grant it autocephaly. Serbs were finally free in the religious and political sense. The church grew with the expansion of the Kingdom and the Serbian Archdiocese officially became the Patriarchate in 1346.

The empowerment of the Serbian church, and the preaching in their language that was implied and taken at that time as a divine language, in spite of the Albanians who did not gain this right in time, left serious and dark consequences in shaping the true history of the Balkans. It was clear that even Orthodox Albanians had to perform the sacraments and baptisms of infants in the Serbian language/alphabet. Throughout the middle ages, intentionally or unintentionally, this influenced not only the ethnic assimilation of Orthodox Albanians but also the absorption of their glorious history, culture, and their heroes. This tendency, although wrong, was somewhat

normal for a people who had no cultural past and sought in any way a strong foundation in this regard. In some South Slavic churches, the Serbian language came to be referred to as the Illyrian language and was marked as "iliryca lingua". The Bulgarians began to call their language Macedonian (ie Illyrian), and after conquering Macedonia, they named Alexander the Great their ancestor. Even today, in Northern Macedonia, where the Bulgarian leadership dominates, this hero of antiquity is still officially considered theirs, and by no means the Albanians. The French historian D'Angeliel writes: "It cannot be forgotten that Alexander the Great was of Illyrian descent, of Hellenic education, and brought up by another Albanian / Illyrian from Stragia, Macedonia, Aristotle. Alexander the Great's mother, Olympia / Olympia, was from the Illyrian-Epirote tribes, his father, Philip II, was Macedonian Illyrian, so Albanian... "

The genesis and the beginning of the history of the Slavs of Balkans, and in particular of Serbian history, was made by the Chronicles of Serbians' monks - deified, with myths on a race basis, hyperbolic, false, and one-sided, so much so that it fascinated their descendants, which remained an incurable mania and obsession that continues to this day. The main hero of the Battle of Kosovo in 1389 was made official and is known in history as the Serbian martyr Milos Obiliq, who was in fact an Albanian Orthodox Milosh Kopiliq. Thus, even to these days, the history of the Balkans and the origin of its peoples is very confusing and dubious and constantly makes historians confused. The losers, in a long term, lose their dignity, and unfortunately, as was

the case with Albanians; they lost also their own history due to delayed incorporation into western educational system. In the other words, they were naked not only physically but also spiritually. The winners, slavs, absorbed their glorious past history into their own, and made it officially as the history of Balkans. Only informally, by rhapsodies and folk songs, the remaining survived Albanians could manage to preserve some of their glorious history. Skanderbeg, the main and irreplaceable Albanian hero, today would be known as the official Serbian national hero, if it were not for Frang Bardhi (Franciscus Blancus 1606–1643 an Albanian Catholic bishop and writer) who wrote a biography, called *The Apology of Scanderbeg* published in Venice in 1636. *The Apology of Scanderbeg* was a polemic against Slavic Catholic priest Ivan Tomko Mrnavić, who claimed that Kastrioti was of Slav origin.

“Religion is too important to be left in the hands of people who believe in it. Finally, historians are coming to grips with this simple truth,” as David A. Hollinger (USA historian) stated.

The rise of the losers will cause the winners to fall. The plan of complete partition of Albania, and the tendency of complete extinction of Albanians was canceled and mitigated thanks to the reactions and political influence of the United States of America, with President Woodrow Wilson at the Paris Peace Conference of 1919. Despite this, Serbs, Slavic Greeks, and Bulgarians continuously used other programs and projects, even at the academic level, for the physical and spiritual extinction of the Albanians.

Nobel Prize winner Ivo Andric, as a Serbian intellectual, was shocked to discover that the old Albanian language and the true Albanian history of antiquity, if it could ever be published, would pose a fatal danger that would lead to the shaking and decline of its state dignity, history and culture with which it was grown and inspired. The same applies for Bulgarians' Macedonia and Greece history.

A famous Austrian linguist, Maximilian Lambertz, declared: "True world history will be written only when Albanians will take part in its compilation."

Therefore, Ivo Andric himself, together with academic Vaso Cubrilovic, Ilija Garashanin, and the others, inspired by the "Sacred Serbian Doctrine", were engaged in the compilation of a "secret" plan for the extinction of autochthonous Albanians in Serbia, and colonization of their lands by the Serbs. The sacred Serbian doctrine of the annihilation and expulsion of the Albanian element from their ethnic lands dates back to the moment of the infiltration of the Slavic people in the Balkans (XII century), and emerges from the mania of Serbian monks of the Orthodox Church, continuing and institutionalizing in the nineteenth and twentieth centuries by the authorities mentioned above.

On the other hand, Albania remained as a small and weak official state with a still naive diplomacy, which has recently been released from a long miserable isolation of the Enver's communist government, and admits continued attacks and provocations at the diplomatic level from

Greece, Bulgaria and Serbia, if it would dare to change anything in its official history. Unfortunately, even today, the "secret plan" of the sacred doctrine of Serbia, Slavo-Greece and Bulgarian-Macedonia has never ceased and is active with other tools and strategies, and the true Albanian history has not been written yet.

Albanians as Orthodox Christians, Catholics, and Muslims

The conversion to Islam of the Albanians while administrated by the Ottomans in the Balkans during the five centuries, although it cannot be said by force, especially those from the vilayet of Kosovo, can be taken as a phenomenon of resistance to Slavic pressures and atrocities from their orthodox churches. Scholar Edith Durham writes of the Slavic Orthodox Church during the middle ages: "The Orthodox Church, with its anti - Semitic programs in Russia and its actions in the Balkans, now holds the record for religious atrocities."

Slavic churches were allowed by the Ottoman Empire because the Slavs in time succumbed to the Eastern superpower that overthrew Byzantium, subjecting it to agreements with them. Moreover, in the 16th century, the Serbian Patriarchate was able to gain from Ottoman power the right to place Albanian Catholics under its jurisdiction. In 1694 the Albanian Archbishop Andrea Bogdani of Shkup (present-day Skopje, Northern Macedonia), who at the time

belonged to the vilayet of Kosovo, declared before the congregation in Rome that Albanian Catholics were persecuted far more by the Serbian Orthodox Church than by the Ottoman administration. This existential crisis stems from the weak Albanian ecclesiastical power because neither before the conquest nor after the conquest by the Ottomans, the evangelical Albanians failed to have their national church like the Slavs for a very long time. However, what distinguished them and kept them united and unique, despite their religions, was mainly their glorious past, shared folklore, their white *plis*, the red and black flag, and most importantly in terms of ethics and morality - their ancient code. Thus, the conversion of Albanians to Islam in the vilayet of Kosovo, with the exception of some of its mountain villages remaining Roman Catholic, although useful in preserving ethnicity from Slavic ecclesiastical powers and pressures for five centuries, proved tragic with the fall and withdrawal of the Ottoman Empire, just at the beginning of the formation of the Balkan states.

During these times of Ottoman occupation, Serbian Patriarchate continued to enrich its history where every Albanian Orthodox in the Balkans with heroic deeds was absorbed in their "glorious" Serbian history. That time "Albanians" were called with different names like: Epirotes, Arbëneshtë, Arvanitas, and religiously were "divided" into Islam, orthodox and catholic.

The fall of the Ottoman Empire – the beginning of another “divine horror”

The formation of the Balkan states began with the fall of the Ottoman Empire, as the last multi-ethnic Islamic empire in history, starting from the middle of the XIX century. But with this fall, another apocalypse began for the Albanians of the Balkans, surrounded by Slavs on three sides - the Serbs, Bulgarians, and Greeks. Here, I will only mention the fate of those Albanians who lived in the cities and villages of the Sanjak of Niš, present Serbia, numbering up to 200,000 inhabitants based on Austro- Hungarian statistics.

Inflated and mesmerized by "divine history" and myths, with the weakening of the Ottomans, Serbs blessed by the priests, began uprisings and the war against them. But what is remembered by the world and newspapers of that time, is not their heroic war against the declining army of Turkey, but the expulsion of the Albanian civilians' population from these regions done in a satanic manner that today could be classified as a heavy genocide and ethnic cleansing. Among the most serious crimes was the slaughtering of babies in the wombs of Albanian pregnant mothers. This apocalypse continued throughout the First World War and continued until 1941. The epilogue of the secret treaty of London in 1913 and the peace treaty of Versailles in 1919 deepened the consequences for the Albanian nation. "Serbian, Montenegrin, Bulgarian and Greek invading armies in the Albanian areas occupied

during the Balkan Wars (1912-13) and during the First World War (1914-18) completely destroyed more than 800 Albanian localities, killed or permanently destroyed about 350,000 Albanians and more than 500,000 others followed from the ethnic hearths” as per press.

Excerpt from work by Leo Freundlich: Albania’s Golgotha: Indictment of the Exterminators of the Albanian People: “Houses and whole villages reduced to ashes, unarmed and innocent populations massacred en masse, incredible acts of violence, pillage and brutality of every kind – such were the means which were employed and are still being employed by the Serbo-Montenegrin soldiery, with a view to the entire transformation of the ethnic character of regions inhabited exclusively by Albanians”.

– Report of the International Commission on the Balkan Wars: “In the early 20th century, the Ottoman Empire, which had ruled the Albanian region of Kosova for five centuries, was in disarray. Filling the vacuum, Serb troops invaded the territory to claim and occupy it for Serbia and to cleanse it of its Albanian population. The Ambassadors’ Conference in London proposed drawing the borders of Albania according to ethnic and religious statistics to be gathered on-site by a commission. The Serbs hastened to prepare the statistics for them with machine guns, rifles, and bayonets. When Serbian imperialists invaded Kosova, they informed the world that they would return again the historical rights they had in 1389 (the battle of Kosovo fought by the Serbian Empire against the invading Muslims). Basing themselves on these “historical rights,”

Italy, France, Greece, or Turkey could rise and request to get half of Europe, as they once had these regions in their hands. Furthermore, France could request a part of Russia, as Napoleon went once to Moscow in 1812.”

George Fred Williams from the USA was appointed Minister to Greece and Montenegro by President Woodrow Wilson, serving in 1914. He resigned this position after a visit to Albania witnessing the tragic Albanian civilians being murdered and left to die of hunger by the Royal Greek Army. He wrote: “It is a tragedy beyond any imagination that this great and very ancient race comes to this condition, which deserves to be called the scandal of the European civilization. It is not surprising that the Ottoman conqueror stopped any digging on Albanian soil, which could remind the people of its former glory...”

Kosova - will ever be left in peace?

I was born in Gjilan, Kosovo, and experienced my youth in the environment of Tito’s socialist Yugoslavia—a statesman of Croatian descent who was wise and brave enough to keep the Slavic peoples, as well as the Albanians, united. His motto was: “Let us preserve brotherhood and unity as the pupil of our eye.”

Although it was a socialist state, Tito allowed the preaching and rituals of religious institutions. But at that time, with a very favorable standard of living, regular religious rituals

were practiced only by the small and elderly strata of the population. "The brighter the night, the darker the stars. The less sorrow, the farther God is!"

Interethnic peace and harmony did not last long. Ten years after Tito's death, with the rise of Slobodan Milošević on the Serbian political stage within Yugoslavia, the old mania of Orthodox Church politics resurfaced. The demons from "divine stories and histories" awakened again. Yugoslavia quickly disintegrated, and the next "Balkan" war erupted; this time only among the nations that had once formed Yugoslavia, culminating in the Kosovo War in 1999.

After the war, an uncle on my mother's side, Uncle Shaban, who had emigrated to Turkey, returned to visit his birthplace, Gjilan. On this occasion, he had come to tend to the graves of his parents. When we met, among other things, I said to him, "You should leave Turkey and come back here, uncle. It's over. We won!" He looked at me with a gentle smile and replied, "Listen carefully to what your uncle is telling you: Kosovo will never be left in peace. Remember this."

A few days later, I heard that he had returned to Turkey. A few years after that, he passed away.

Fifteen years later, while watching the news on a screen, I was deeply shaken when I saw with my own eyes an orthodox priest in Serbia blessing soldiers in preparation for another possible war against the Albanians of Kosovo. In that moment, I recalled, and fully understood, the words

of my uncle. Faced with this form of chronic obsession, ideological mania, and a language with hateful dogma within a neighboring state, rooted in an inflated and mythologized sense of “divine” history, Kosovo, it seemed to me, would never truly be left in peace.

Conclusion

Religion, as an institution and as an executive power in the hands of naive, wild, and evil hearts, has appeared as the most terrible image of humanity. Likewise, pure atheists are no different from extreme religious fanatics. These two opposites are nothing but the same miserable worlds. One dark black, the other dull white, colors without taste, joy, life, or freedom; a fanatical fundamentalist religious state and a communist-monarchist state like that of Stalin or Enver.

On the other hand, religion has proven to be positive when understood as an ideology of hope and moral stability within the complexity of human life. After all, religions, like myths, make us feel warmer, enrich the soul and imagination, and strengthen our courage along the journey and mission of life.

As long as we cannot find answers to the fundamental questions through science, religions will never disappear. And this will last forever, “...to the end of time.”